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A REVIEW OF INNOVATIONS IN WATER-GAS SHIFT AND STEAM REFORMING FOR HYDROGEN PRODUCTION

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Abstrakt. Hydrogen is considered the clean fuel of the future, with the highest mass-based energy density among known fuels. Water gas shift (WGS) and steam reforming (SR) are the main reactions used for hydrogen production, and improved catalysts are essential for the future of WGS and SR processes. Major advances have been made recently in various aspects of these fields, including approaches to preparation and characterization, doping and promotion, and evaluation of catalysts, especially nanocatalysts. Significant progress has been made in improving the stability of catalysts, overall feedstock conversion, and selectivity of hydrogen production. The aim of this review is to introduce these hydrogen production processes, present developments in these areas, and discuss recent advances that have had notable impacts.

Introduction

Environmental concerns about greenhouse gas emissions have become a major issue that has prompted the development and application of techniques to reduce the impact of fossil fuel combustion [1]. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) capture is a technology that can be applied to existing plants that produce large amounts of CO₂, and as new efficient technologies are developed, its application to existing plants is becoming a more viable option [2], [3], [4], [5]. CO₂ emissions can also be reduced by using alternative fuels for energy production methods, such as the use of hydrogen (H₂), the production of which will be investigated in this study. Hydrogen is one of many fuel options for the future and is particularly attractive because it can be stored and transported efficiently and burns cleanly, producing only water as a byproduct. Although hydrogen production from fossil fuels is not sustainable, a stable supply of renewable fuels is currently not possible. Some promising renewable technologies for hydrogen production include water splitting and biogas reforming. Water splitting separates oxygen and hydrogen from water and breaks these bonds by various methods, such as photoelectrochemical decomposition, photocatalysis, and electrolysis. Photoelectrochemical (PEC) water splitting uses a PEC cell that contains a photocatalyst-coated anode, an electrocatalyst-coated cathode, and an electrolyte that together generates electron-hole pairs that drive oxidation and reduction reactions [6], [7], [8], [9]. The use of particulate photocatalysts for direct conversion is also an important area of research, as it is a one-step conversion process using a single catalyst instead of two catalysts as in PEC [10]. Since sunlight does not have a high enough energy density to enable high-energy activities such as transportation, these processes allow the energy from the sun to be stored and used later. Another renewable source of hydrogen is biogas reforming, and bioethanol produced from biomass is a typical biogas [11], [12], [13]. Biomass is usually obtained from agricultural crops, although some plants are grown exclusively for energy production. Neither water splitting nor biogas reforming is a mature technology that can be applied on a large scale. Therefore, hydrogen production from fossil fuels

can meet energy needs in an environmentally conscious manner, facilitating immediate reductions in greenhouse gas emissions. Many things need to happen for hydrogen to become a viable fuel option. It needs to be produced in larger quantities in a clean and efficient manner, the infrastructure needs to be put in place to distribute the hydrogen to customers, and the production costs need to be reduced. The deployment of infrastructure by industry depends on a stable and efficient supply, so the first step in hydrogen energy production is to develop methods to ensure that these requirements are met. To reduce production costs, catalysts need to be found that can increase the activity of the water gas shift (WGS) and steam reforming (SR) reactions, the main producers of hydrogen, while at the same time reducing the problems encountered with traditional catalysts, such as low conversion, high energy demand, and deactivation during startup and shutdown [14], [15], [16].

Reforming of gaseous fuels is currently the main source of hydrogen. In 2012, SR from methane (CH_4) accounted for 95% of hydrogen production in the United States [17]. The SR reaction (R1) uses methane and steam to produce H_2 and carbon monoxide (CO). The CO can be further converted using the WGS reaction (R2) to produce additional hydrogen by converting CO and steam to CO_2 and H_2 . Together, these reactions form an overall reaction (R3) that converts methane to carbon dioxide and hydrogen [18], [19].

To achieve large amounts of H_2 production, a catalyst that facilitates activation must be selected. Traditional catalysts are intolerant to poisons and require special activation procedures [20]. Recently, many studies have focused on catalysts that can overcome these problems, as well as achieve a theoretical yield of nearly 100% hydrogen in WGS and SR reactions, while also increasing stability and reducing energy input [21], [22]. Although single metal systems on activated supports have been extensively studied and characterized, a more innovative approach to hydrogen production through catalysis comes in the form of bimetallics. Bimetallics can have capabilities that are very different from those of the individual metals that compose them. These features, as well as the extremely promising results of previous studies, have led to an increase in research focused on bimetallic compounds. Higher conversions and selectivities are achieved by using bimetallics with dispersed nanoscale interacting particles. On the contrary, these compounds are more difficult to prepare and characterize due to the presence of additional metals [17]. A large number of metal-support combinations have been investigated, some of which have outperformed traditional catalysts by a large margin. These new catalysts have not only increased the conversion of desired gases, but also increased the selectivity, stability, and energy costs required for the conversion.

Reforming

Steam reforming can be used with a wide variety of feedstocks, including methane, ethane, methanol, ethanol, acetone, and higher hydrocarbons, and much research has been devoted to the characterization of catalysts using these feedstocks. Methane has received much attention due to its favorable byproduct formation compared to other feeds [17]. Methanol and ethanol are increasingly being studied, and a number of reaction mechanisms have been proposed. Common products of gasification and reforming include CO_2 , which the WGS reaction converts while producing additional hydrogen, making WGS very important for increasing hydrogen production. WGS is a generally exothermic system

Common Problems with Reforming and WGS Catalysts

SR and WGS reactions are affected by many variables, including reaction conditions such as temperature and pressure, S/C ratio, feedstock used, reactor properties and residence time; and physical parameters such as catalyst composition, additive dispersion, sintering and poisoning. All of these factors affect how the catalyst performs and can produce very different results. The same catalyst can produce very different results due to these variations, and to account for these.

Conclusion

Advances in catalysis technologies and methods have improved the status of SR and WGS. Nanoscale particle synthesis methods, including impregnation, co-spraying, and chemical vapor deposition, allow for highly dispersed additives and high activity. The addition of metal or bimetallic species to the catalyst can improve selectivity, durability, and activity. Many typical problems

associated with catalysts, including coke formation, active agents, can be overcome by the addition of these metals.

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